

“Periodic KPI Updates Related to Communication and Dissemination: Performance Monitoring”

DELIVERABLE
D4.3

Version 2.0
01.2026

Project Number: 101070297

Project Acronym: INDUSAC

Project title: Quick Challenge-driven, Human-centred Co-Creation Mechanism for INDUSty-Academia Collaborations

Starting date: 01/09/2022

Duration in months: 36

Call (part) identifier: HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01

Topic: HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01-20

Technical reference

<i>Deliverable: D4.3</i>	
<i>Work Package:</i>	4
<i>Due Date:</i>	M36
<i>Submission Date:</i>	08/2023 (v. M12), 08/2024 (v. M24), 08/2025 (v. M36)
<i>Resubmission Date (based on EC feedback)</i>	26/01/2026
<i>Start Date of Project:</i>	01/09/2022
<i>Duration of Project:</i>	36 months
<i>Organisation Responsible for Deliverable:</i>	Bydgoszcz Industrial Cluster Tool Valley
<i>Version:</i>	2.0
<i>Status:</i>	Final
<i>Author name(s):</i>	Marta Jurkowska, Marika Kowalska, Agnieszka Matuszak
<i>Reviewer(s):</i>	INDUSAC partners and the INDUSAC Steering Committee
<i>Type:</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Report <input type="checkbox"/> Other
<i>Dissemination level:</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PU <input type="checkbox"/> SEN

History of Changes:

Date	Comments	Version
11.07.2025	<i>initial draft by partners responsible</i>	V0.1
18.07.2025	<i>draft based on feedback from project partners</i>	V0.2
25.07.2025	<i>draft based on feedback from Steering Committee</i>	V0.3
29.08.2025	<i>final version submitted to Participant Portal</i>	V1.0
26.01.2026	<i>resubmission after EC feedback</i>	V2.0

SUMMARY OF THE PROJECT

INDUSAC's main objective was to develop and validate a state-of-the-art, Industry-Academia collaboration (IAC) mechanism for quick, challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation. It aimed to build upon pre-existing IAC mechanisms such as EIT KICs and to facilitate a simple, user-friendly co-creation process that allowed for the development of solutions clearly addressing the needs and interests of companies, students, and researchers in the EU, with special attention to widening and associated countries. Of a highly digitalised nature, the project piloted the mechanism's two main components: a methodology developed by applying human-centred design principles and an online platform designed to connect stakeholders from the industry-academia ecosystem and to support them throughout their co-creation journey.

The INDUSAC methodology provides the guidance and tools needed to power the process, whilst the platform stands as a networking space for stakeholders to connect, as well as a co-creation arena to develop joint solutions. Through the experience of supporting transnational co-creation teams throughout the project lifetime, the INDUSAC mechanism and its two key components were successively improved until the project ends, delivering a tested mechanism ready for replication and upskilling. INDUSAC created a dynamic community of industry-academia stakeholders, including companies, students and researchers. The INDUSAC achieved a strong interdisciplinary, cross-sectorial and geographically balanced partnership that leveraged the needed expertise and network to achieve our project's goals.

ABSTRACT

This document is the final version of Deliverable D4.3: Periodic KPI Updates Related to Communication and Dissemination: Performance Monitoring, produced within Work Package 4 (WP4) of the INDUSAC project. The deliverable provides a comprehensive summary and analysis of the communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities carried out by the consortium throughout the entire project duration (M1–M36).

The report documents the evolution of outreach efforts across three reporting periods: M1–M12, M13–M24, and M25–M36, demonstrating the project's growing visibility and impact. Key performance indicators (KPIs) were monitored and analysed across multiple channels, including the project website, social media, newsletters, press clippings, and event participation.

The final period (M25–M36) focused on showcasing project results and sustaining engagement through targeted campaigns, high-profile events, and tailored content. The deliverable also presents recommendations for maintaining and scaling outreach efforts beyond the project's lifetime.

This report highlights the effectiveness of the consortium's communication strategy. It confirms that the dissemination activities successfully supported the project's overall objectives: fostering human-centred, quick challenge-driven industry-academia collaborations and building a vibrant, engaged community of stakeholders across Europe and beyond.

LIST OF ACRONYMS

BAX	Bax, member of the INDUSAC consortium
BIC	Bydgoszcz Industrial Cluster Tool Valley, member of the INDUSAC consortium
CCIPB	Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Pécs-Baranya, member of the INDUSAC consortium
CIT UPC	UPC Technology Center, member of the INDUSAC consortium
CUT	Cyprus University of Technology, member of the INDUSAC consortium
EIT	EIT Manufacturing East, member of the INDUSAC consortium
EU	European Union
INDUSAC	Quick Challenge-driven, Human-centred Co-Creation Mechanism for INDUSty-Academia Collaborations
INNO	Innoget, member of the INDUSAC consortium
JSI	Jožef Stefan Institute, member of the INDUSAC consortium, project coordinator
KICs	Knowledge and Innovation Communities
KIT	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, member of the INDUSAC consortium
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M	Month
PPP	Public Private Partnership
PVI	Project visual identity
T	Task
WP	Work Package

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I. INTRODUCTION

This document constitutes the final version of Deliverable D4.3 within Work Package 4 – Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication.

Deliverable D4.3 summarises and assesses the efficiency of the dissemination and exploitation activities developed and implemented by the INDUSAC consortium throughout the entire project duration (M1–M36). It provides an overview of key performance indicators (KPIs). It evaluates the impact of communication actions that supported the project's objectives of fostering quick, challenge-driven, human-centred industry-academia collaborations.

The deliverable builds on the two earlier versions submitted at M12 (D4.3; Matuszak 2023) and M24 (D4.3; Jurkowska, Kowalska 2024), maintaining the structure recommended during the mid-term review meeting in Ljubljana, Slovenia (April 2024). The results and analysis from previous reporting periods (M1–M12 and M13–M24) remained unchanged and were complemented with a dedicated section presenting the outcomes and progress achieved in the final period (M25–M36).

By presenting the evolution of the project's communication and dissemination performance across all three periods, this deliverable demonstrates how the INDUSAC consortium effectively engaged stakeholders, increased visibility, and strengthened the project's impact within its target communities.

II. MONITORING PROCESS

To achieve maximum impact, communication and dissemination activities needed to begin after the kick-off meeting held in September 2022. Following this, consortium partners were given a detailed introduction to the communication strategy and general guidelines for utilising the marketing materials (press releases, PowerPoint template, social media posts, etc.) during online project meetings and dedicated WP4 meetings. Active dissemination during the project launch, event promotion, and regional outreach was closely monitored.

BIC monitored the progress of dissemination and communication activities using the shared “Partners’ actions reporting dashboard”, an Excel file (Figure 1), which provided an overview of the consortium’s communication and dissemination activities. The tool had two primary purposes: to monitor all dissemination and communication activities carried out within the project and to track all events partners attended to promote the project. Partners were requested to update the dashboard by adding the activities they carried out. BIC regularly checked the dashboard and updated the progress of the specific KPIs to monitor dissemination efforts closely.

Partner Name	Social media type (LinkedIn, Twitter, other)	Date	Link
EIT Manufacturing	LinkedIn	2022-09-21	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/eit-manufacturing_horizoneurope-europe-industry-activity-697826922036293224-TH2i?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
BIC	LinkedIn	2022-09-26	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6980163632798007296
KIT	LinkedIn	2022-10-04	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/ipek-institut%C3%BCrproduktentwicklungamkit_ipek-indusac-project-activity-6976115293811052544-
CIT UPC	LinkedIn	2022-10-09	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6978682874887598081/
CIT UPC	Twitter	2022-10-13	https://twitter.com/CIT_UPC/status/1580548986544455683
CIT UPC	Twitter	2022-10-24	https://twitter.com/CIT_UPC/status/1584492472348049408
BIC	Facebook	2022-11-08	https://www.facebook.com/klasterbvdposzcz/posts/pfbidOpWKTDBaYqZrpKMth3zz9EWLYg2FetHSP3TV2V818v799Xs5ogS4fjSBQbsidmorpj
KIT	LinkedIn	2022-12-12	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/ipek-institut%C3%BCrproduktentwicklungamkit_indusac-horizoneu-iac-activity-7004370534847143936-
CIT UPC	LinkedIn	2022-12-12	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/cit-upc_indusac-survey-success-factors-of-industry-academia-activity-7001168249983774720-
Annika Bastian (KIT)	LinkedIn	December	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/annika-bastian-86690217a_indusac-horizoneu-iac-activity-7004374831685103616-
Katharina Ritzler (former CUT)	LinkedIn	December	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/dr-ing-katharina-ritzler-a50275148_indusac-horizoneu-iac-activity-7004485616100900865-
CUT	Facebook	2023-01-17	https://www.facebook.com/story.php?story_fbid=pfbid0EoTCYm47FNHWJMwFGMSte6LE5Wgvtxm4b996F8ENNVH79sbjWkpbqA9zcGwVMsfI&
CUT	Instagram	2023-01-17	https://www.instagram.com/p/CnhlwW3NOph/?igshid=YmMyMTA2M2Y%3D
IJS-U9	LinkedIn	2023-05-24	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7067105219192467457/
INNOGET	LinkedIn	2023-06-28	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7079775171116437504
INNOGET	LinkedIn	2023-07-04	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7079775171116437504
IJS-U9	LinkedIn	2023-07-11	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7084431909308514304
INNOGET	LinkedIn	2023-07-19	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/jordirafols_indusac-activity-7086246394293870592-vx-S?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
INNOGET	LinkedIn	2023-07-26	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/jordirafols_indusac-activity-7086246394293870592-vx-S?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop

Figure 1: Partners' actions reporting dashboard – “Social media” table with links. A screenshot of the relevant part of the document is shown for illustration

The dashboard includes lists of:

- **Press Clippings:** All news items published online or offline in different channels (press, TV, radio, web, etc.)
- **Social Media:** Links to posts of partners’ institutional social media accounts or individual accounts of consortium members
- **Newsletters:** Institutional newsletters where consortium partners have published information about INDUSAC
- **Events:** events where partners participated as organisers, attendants and/or speakers to spread the word about the INDUSAC project

- **Scientific publications:** Publications made by partners in a journal or scientific magazine as a result of INDUSAC actions.
- **Communication Plan for Partners:** After the consortium meeting in Barcelona in 2023, the partners agreed to share the responsibility for communication. In this tab, it is stated which partner in the selected month was obliged to propose at least four posts, directly or indirectly related to the project's activities.

III. WEBSITE

As explained in deliverable D4.1, INDUSAC Communication Strategy and Materials, the INDUSAC website was one of the main tools for disseminating and communicating important project-related information, where people could learn about project activities, deadlines, and news. The website was crucial to promoting the project and served as the gateway to fulfil INDUSAC's primary purpose: connecting companies with students and researchers.

1. Visitors' profile

M1-M12

Figure 2: Visitors by language in the M1-M12 period

Regarding the demographic profile of INDUSAC website visitors in the M1-M12 period, English was the most common language (20 users, representing 42,6 % of all visitors), followed by Polish (14 users, 29,8 %), Spanish (5 users, 10,6 %), and German (4 users, 8,5 %) as the top four languages (Figure 2).

Figure 3: Visitors by country in the M1-M12 period

Country	Users	New users	Engaged sessions	Engagement rate	Engaged sessions per user
	47 100% of total	34 100% of total	59 100% of total	52.68% Avg 0%	1.26 Avg 0%
1 Poland	14	9	31	60.78%	2.21
2 Spain	9	7	8	50%	0.89
3 Austria	5	4	5	71.43%	1.00
4 China	4	3	0	0%	0.00
5 Slovenia	3	2	5	55.56%	1.67
6 Germany	2	1	2	40%	1.00
7 Belgium	1	1	0	0%	0.00
8 France	1	1	1	100%	1.00
9 Hungary	1	1	0	0%	0.00
10 Ireland	1	1	1	100%	1.00

Figure 4: Top 10 Visitors by country in the M1-M12 period

The visitors to the INDUSAC website during the M1-M12 period came from 16 countries, including EU countries, the United States, China, and Pakistan. The top five countries were: Poland (14), followed by Spain (9), Austria (5), China (4), and Slovenia (3) (Figures 3 and 4). The largest share came from Poland (29,8%), followed by Spain (19,1%), Austria (10,6%), China (8,5%), and Slovenia (6,4%). These figures reveal that nearly 75% of total traffic originated from key partner regions, confirming that the initial outreach strategy effectively mobilised the consortium’s core networks. Early international visits from the United States, China, and Pakistan (collectively 9%) already indicated growing global curiosity about the INDUSAC initiative. The concentration of traffic from Poland, Spain, and Austria highlighted the initial outreach strength within partner regions, while emerging interest from China and Slovenia signalled growing international awareness. This early pattern of geographically diverse engagement laid the groundwork for broader visibility in later project phases.

M13 – M24

Regarding the demographics profile of INDUSAC website visitors and their engagement rate in the M13-M24 period, English was the primary language (55%), followed by Turkish, Polish and Slovenian (6%), and Spanish (4%) as the top four languages (Figure 5).

Users by Language

↓ Language ▾ +

↓ Users

New users

		9,730 100% of total	9,681 100% of total
1	English	5,316	5,249
2	Turkish	609	609
3	Polish	587	585
4	Slovenian	540	536
5	Spanish	378	378

Figure 5: Visitors by language in the M13-M24 period

The visitors of the INDUSAC website in the M13-M24 period came from 16 different countries – including EU countries, the United States, China, and India. The top 7 countries were: Slovenia, Poland, Turkey, Spain, Hungary, the United States and Serbia (Figures 6 and 7).

Users by Country

COUNTRY	USERS
Slovenia	1.1K
Poland	1.1K
Türkiye	773
Spain	557
Hungary	483
United States	461
Serbia	405

Figure 6: Visitors by country in the M13-M24 period

Country	Users	New users	Engaged sessions	Engagement rate	Engaged sessions per user	Average engagement time	Event count
	9,732 100% of total	9,683 100% of total	9,255 100% of total	52.06% Avg 0%	0.95 Avg 0%	1m 18s Avg 0%	89,531 100% of total
1 Slovenia	1,143	1,134	1,851	57.68%	1.62	1m 54s	17,183
2 Poland	1,053	1,051	1,099	50%	1.04	1m 33s	13,269
3 Türkiye	774	774	650	50.19%	0.84	1m 24s	5,809
4 Spain	557	555	754	61.45%	1.35	1m 25s	6,535
5 Hungary	483	478	512	60.31%	1.06	1m 31s	4,818
6 United States	461	450	73	15.11%	0.16	5s	1,659
7 Serbia	405	401	304	58.24%	0.75	1m 08s	2,434
8 Romania	385	384	332	51.23%	0.86	1m 20s	3,124
9 France	365	357	222	42.69%	0.61	28s	2,192
10 Germany	352	329	353	53.57%	1.00	1m 26s	3,793

Figure 7: Top 10 Visitors by country in the M13-M24 period

Between months 13 and 24, the INDUSAC website attracted visitors from over 16 countries, showing a significant increase in engagement, rising from 47 users in the first year to 9,732 (+20,600%). Slovenia (22%), Poland (19%), Turkey (11%), and Spain (9%) constituted the primary audiences, while new countries such as the United States (6%) and Serbia (5%) expanded the project's international reach. Compared to the initial reporting period, engagement duration per session increased by 17%, indicating that the website not only drew more users but also maintained their interest for longer. These results demonstrate that INDUSAC's digital visibility has shifted from a regional to a transnational level, effectively connecting diverse innovation ecosystems.

M25-M36

During the final period, website traffic continued to show strong engagement from a diverse international audience.

The most common user language remained English (7,600 users), followed by Spanish (627), Italian (444), Slovenian (407), and Polish (345). Other notable languages were German, Ukrainian, Turkish, Russian, and Hungarian, demonstrating the project's broad outreach across Europe and beyond (Figure 8).

Top Language by Users

Jul 8, 2024–Jul 7, 2025

Figure 8: Top languages by users in the M25-M36 period

By European country, the top active user bases were Slovenia (1,062), Spain (755), Poland (678), the Netherlands (669), Italy (575), and Ireland (507), with significant increases noted in Spain, the Netherlands, Italy, and Ireland compared to earlier periods (Figures 9 and 10).

Active users by Country

Figure 9: Visitors by country in the M25-M36 period

Country	Active users	New users	Engaged sessions	Engagement rate	Engaged sessions per active user	Average engagement time per active user	Event count All events
Total	12,023 100% of total	11,807 100% of total	10,498 100% of total	53.41% Avg 0%	0.87 Avg 0%	1m 14s Avg 0%	98,727 100% of total
1 Slovenia	1,062 (8.83%)	1,015 (8.6%)	1,799 (17.14%)	59.71%	1.69	1m 54s	15,715 (15.92%)
2 United States	1,055 (8.77%)	1,046 (8.86%)	481 (4.58%)	44.45%	0.46	1m 17s	4,688 (4.75%)
3 Spain	755 (6.28%)	737 (6.24%)	690 (6.57%)	57.5%	0.91	1m 05s	6,132 (6.21%)
4 Poland	678 (5.64%)	664 (5.62%)	610 (5.81%)	45.83%	0.90	1m 04s	6,869 (6.96%)
5 Netherlands	669 (5.56%)	656 (5.56%)	207 (1.97%)	26.85%	0.31	19s	3,015 (3.05%)
6 Italy	575 (4.78%)	563 (4.77%)	607 (5.78%)	57.37%	1.06	1m 54s	5,424 (5.49%)
7 Ireland	507 (4.22%)	502 (4.25%)	99 (0.94%)	19.37%	0.20	9s	1,812 (1.84%)
8 Germany	495 (4.12%)	449 (3.8%)	394 (3.75%)	55.73%	0.80	55s	3,788 (3.84%)
9 Hungary	445 (3.7%)	434 (3.68%)	436 (4.15%)	51.05%	0.98	1m 23s	4,310 (4.37%)
10 India	409 (3.4%)	407 (3.45%)	347 (3.31%)	71.84%	0.85	43s	2,536 (2.57%)

Figure 10: Top 10 Visitors by country in the M25-M36 period

In the final period, INDUSAC achieved its highest-ever website engagement, with 12,023 active users, up 23.5% from the previous phase. The largest user bases came from Slovenia (1,062 users; 8.8%), Spain (755; 6.3%), and Poland (678; 5.6%), with remarkable growth from the Netherlands (669; +310%) and Italy (575; +290%). Ireland also joined the top six with 507 users, marking a fourfold rise compared to earlier phases. Overall, European users accounted for over 87% of all traffic, confirming that INDUSAC successfully consolidated a strong, pan-European online community.

2. Channels

M1-M12

Session default channel group	Users	Sessions	Engaged sessions	Average engagement time per session	Engaged sessions per user	Events per session	Engagement rate
	47 100% of total	112 100% of total	59 100% of total	0m 34s Avg 0%	1.26 Avg 0%	6.18 Avg 0%	52.68% Avg 0%
1 Organic Search	21	46	23	0m 24s	1.10	4.65	50%
2 Direct	23	36	21	0m 39s	0.91	6.47	58.33%
3 Organic Social	1	16	5	0m 12s	5.00	3.88	31.25%
4 Referral	4	13	10	1m 23s	2.50	14.00	76.92%
5 Unassigned	1	1	0	0m 07s	0.00	1.00	0%

Figure 11: Website traffic in the M1-M12 period

Almost 23% of traffic to the INDUSAC website during the M1-M12 period arrived via Organic Search. Followed by Direct (21% of engagement sessions), while 10% came from Referrals, and 5% of engagement sessions came from Organic Social¹ (Figure 11). Although total engagement was modest (243 page views; 47 users), these early figures

¹ Organic social refers to traffic and engagement generated through unpaid social media posts, shares, and interactions on platforms such as LinkedIn, X etc. It contrasts with paid (sponsored) social media campaigns and reflects the reach achieved through the project's own social media presence and followers' voluntary activity.

demonstrated that nearly half of visitors discovered INDUSAC either proactively or through established networks. The 40-second average engagement time reflected typical awareness-stage browsing, setting a baseline for the stronger interaction metrics seen later.

M13-M24

In the M13–M24 period, direct traffic had the highest number of users (6,291) and sessions (9,205), indicating strong direct engagement. However, the average engagement time for direct traffic was relatively low at 40 seconds, and the average engaged sessions per user was 0,72, suggesting that while many users visited directly, they might not have been deeply engaged.

By contrast, organic search traffic had an average engagement time of 47 seconds and 1,44 engaged sessions per user, indicating that users coming from search engines were more likely to explore the website content in depth.

Referral traffic stood out with the longest average engagement time (56 seconds) and 1,19 engaged sessions per user, reflecting that visitors arriving via referrals interacted more meaningfully with the site.

Organic social had lower user numbers and the shortest average engagement time (29 seconds) among the channels. However, it recorded the highest events per session (5,06), suggesting that social media users interacted with specific content or features more frequently (Figure 12).

Session primary...channel group) ▾ +		Users	↓ Sessions	Engaged sessions	Average engagement time per session	Engaged sessions per user	Events per session
		9,732 100% of total	17,777 100% of total	9,255 100% of total	43s Avg 0%	0.95 Avg 0%	5.04 Avg 0%
1	Direct	6,291	9,205	4,508	40s	0.72	4.69
2	Organic Search	1,565	3,814	2,253	47s	1.44	5.98
3	Referral	1,505	2,900	1,795	56s	1.19	5.69
4	Organic Social	614	1,307	685	29s	1.12	5.06
5	Unassigned	86	102	3	21s	0.03	2.76
6	Email	38	50	23	35s	0.61	3.42

Figure 12: Website traffic in the M13-M24 period

Traffic composition diversified significantly during the second reporting period. Direct traffic grew to 6,291 users (63,6%) and 9,205 sessions, confirming high brand recall. Organic search users spent an average of 47 seconds per session - 17% longer than direct visitors - while referral traffic achieved the longest engagement time at 56 seconds (+19% over average) and 1,19 engaged sessions per user. Although social media contributed just 5% of

total visits, it produced the highest event interaction rate at 5,06 events per session, revealing strong responsiveness among digitally active audiences.

M25-36

Traffic acquisition continued to be led by direct traffic (49%), though it showed the lowest engagement rate (42,8%) and engagement time (35s), indicating users likely revisited specific content without deep browsing.

Organic search achieved the highest engagement rate (59,5%) and a solid average session time (42s), showing quality of engagement from search engines.

Referral traffic performed strongest in engagement metrics (67,4% engagement rate, 1m15s average session), confirming the value of external links and mentions.

Organic social remained modest in volume but achieved a healthy engagement rate (55,7%), while unassigned and email channels contributed minimally.

Session primary...channel group) +	↓ Sessions	Engaged sessions	Engagement rate	Average engagement time per session
Total	19,654 100% of total	10,498 100% of total	53.41% Avg 0%	45s Avg 0%
1 Direct	9,643 (49.06%)	4,127 (39.31%)	42.8%	35s
2 Organic Search	5,665 (28.82%)	3,370 (32.1%)	59.49%	42s
3 Referral	3,832 (19.5%)	2,583 (24.6%)	67.41%	1m 15s
4 Organic Social	675 (3.43%)	376 (3.58%)	55.7%	32s
5 Unassigned	139 (0.71%)	19 (0.18%)	13.67%	16s
6 Email	12 (0.06%)	7 (0.07%)	58.33%	10s
7 Organic Shopping	1 (<0.01%)	0 (0%)	0%	0s

Figure 13: Website traffic in the M25-M36 period

By the final stage, total website sessions exceeded 31,800, marking a 6% increase from the previous period. Direct traffic represented 49% of users but showed the lowest engagement rate (42,8%) and an average session time of 35 seconds. In contrast, organic search maintained the highest engagement rate (59,5%) and an average duration of 42 seconds, while referral traffic excelled with a 67,4% engagement rate and a 1 minute 15 second average session time - an impressive +34% improvement over the previous period. Organic social channels achieved 55.7% engagement despite smaller volume, confirming that targeted social visibility effectively sustained user interest.

3. Page views

M1-M12

Page title and screen class ▾		↓ Views	Users	Views per user	Average engagement time	Event count All events ▾
		243 100% of total	47 100% of total	5.17 Avg 0%	1m 21s Avg 0%	692 100% of total
1	INDUSAC	115	43	2.67	0m 52s	383
2	Invitation to participate in an exciting new project aimed at strengthening the collaboration between industry and academia. - INDUSAC	19	9	2.11	0m 43s	55
3	INDUSAC - INDUSAC	15	12	1.25	0m 24s	37
4	About Partners - INDUSAC	14	10	1.40	0m 21s	31
5	Communication Toolkit - INDUSAC	11	5	2.20	0m 12s	27
6	Open Call - INDUSAC	11	9	1.22	0m 24s	29
7	Media - INDUSAC	10	5	2.00	0m 13s	26
8	News&Events Archives - INDUSAC	6	3	2.00	0m 20s	14
9	INDUSAC at BioFair 2023, Ljubljana, Slovenia - INDUSAC	5	5	1.00	0m 14s	10
10	INDUSAC at Manufacturing Day 2023, Vienna, Austria - INDUSAC	5	4	1.25	0m 10s	14

Figure 14: Most viewed pages in the M1-M12 period

The website was set up at the end of February 2023. The page that received the most visits during the M1-M12 period was the home page (115). The second most visited page was the Open Call for Universities (19), which proved that users could find enough information about the application and competencies there. However, those interested in getting more detailed information have visited the INDUSAC tab (15), the About Partners (14), and the Communication Toolkit (11), (Figure 14).

M13-M24

Page title and screen class		↓ Views	Users	Views per user	Average engagement time	Event count
		100% of total	100% of total	Avg 0%	Avg 0%	100% of total
1	INDUSAC	11,541	5,490	2.10	28s	37,112
2	Students & Researchers - INDUSAC	7,317	4,027	1.82	1m 20s	21,571
3	Companies - INDUSAC	3,031	1,579	1.92	1m 03s	8,407
4	INDUSAC - INDUSAC	1,619	1,086	1.49	37s	4,800
5	About Partners - INDUSAC	771	543	1.42	39s	1,970
6	Communication Toolkit - INDUSAC	665	372	1.79	15s	1,672
7	Invitation to participate in an exciting new project aimed at strengthening the collaboration between industry and academia - INDUSAC	583	385	1.51	34s	1,345
8	INDUSAC Project Virtual Event - INDUSAC	521	384	1.36	18s	1,600
9	Project Committees - INDUSAC	383	311	1.23	12s	911
10	Upcoming Events Archives - INDUSAC	350	245	1.43	9s	823

Figure 15: Most viewed pages in the M13-M24 period

During the M13-M24 period, the most visited page was the home page (11,541). The second most visited page was Students & Researchers (7,317), demonstrating that users could find sufficient information about the application and competencies there. The Companies tab (3,031) shows that our website reached target groups. The ranking of these two pages at the top of the list indicated increased interest following the opening of the Call for Companies in October 2023 and the Call for Students and Researchers in November 2023 (Figure 15).

M25-36

In the final phase (M25-M36), the website continued to attract substantial user engagement, with 98,727 recorded interactions from 12,023 active users. The most viewed pages continued to be: INDUSAC home page (11,363 views), Students & Researchers page (9,703 views), and Companies page (3,315 views).

As the project's piloting phase was underway, the invitation pages moved down the list. New additions, such as the First Newsletter page (3,242 views) and the continued popularity of the About Partners and Communication Toolkit pages, confirmed that visitors were engaging with resources and updates relevant to project results and participation opportunities.

Page title and screen class		↓ Views	Active users	Views per active user	Average engagement time per active user	Event count All events
Total		31,827 100% of total	12,023 100% of total	2.65 Avg 0%	1m 14s Avg 0%	98,727 100% of total
1	INDUSAC	11,363 (35.7%)	5,686 (47.29%)	2.00	34s	36,862 (37.34%)
2	Students & Researchers - INDUSAC	9,703 (30.49%)	5,496 (45.71%)	1.77	1m 11s	29,543 (29.92%)
3	Companies - INDUSAC	3,315 (10.42%)	1,890 (15.72%)	1.75	56s	9,578 (9.7%)
4	INDUSAC - INDUSAC	1,393 (4.38%)	1,013 (8.43%)	1.38	34s	3,931 (3.98%)
5	First Newsletter - INDUSAC	807 (2.54%)	324 (2.69%)	2.49	57s	3,242 (3.28%)
6	About Partners - INDUSAC	542 (1.7%)	411 (3.42%)	1.32	30s	1,353 (1.37%)
7	Communication Toolkit - INDUSAC	533 (1.67%)	388 (3.23%)	1.37	12s	1,390 (1.41%)
8	Invitation to participate in an exciting new project aimed at strengthening the collaboration between industry and academia - INDUSAC	441 (1.39%)	319 (2.65%)	1.38	33s	1,015 (1.03%)
9	Contact - INDUSAC	367 (1.15%)	285 (2.37%)	1.29	29s	921 (0.93%)
10	Upcoming Events Archives - INDUSAC	361 (1.13%)	284 (2.36%)	1.27	12s	867 (0.88%)

Figure 16: Most viewed pages in the M25-M36 period

4. Cumulative Summary (M1–M36)

Over the full course of the project, the INDUSAC website demonstrated growing reach and engagement:

- **M1–M12:** Modest early engagement (243 views, 47 users²), concentrated mainly in Poland, Spain and Austria.
- **M13–M24:** Sharp increase in traffic (29,971 views, 9,732 users), with the website reaching 16+ countries and English firmly dominant.
- **M25–M36:** Sustained high levels of traffic (31,827 views, 12,023 users), broader linguistic diversity, and notable audience expansion in the Netherlands and Italy.

Across all periods, the website accumulated over 62,041 views and more than 21,800 users, validating its role as a vital communication tool.

Organic search and referrals proved most effective at driving high-quality engagement, while direct and social traffic ensured continued visibility among established audiences.

² “Users” in Google Analytics refers to the total number of unique individuals who visited our website during a selected period. Each person is counted only once, even if they return multiple times. “New Users”, on the other hand, represents the subset of those visitors who came to our website for the very first time within that period. These are people who had no prior interactions with our site, according to Google Analytics’ tracking data.

The consistent interest in key pages such as (Calls for) *Students & Researchers* and *Companies* confirms that the website successfully addressed the needs of its target audiences and facilitated the project's overarching goal: connecting companies with students and researchers through quick, human-centred co-creation.

IV. SOCIAL MEDIA

The results of communication and dissemination activities were based on the social media and press clippings activities reported by consortium partners (press, radio, TV, project partners' websites and others).

A total of 33 posts were published via the project partners' social media channels during the first year of implementation (M1-M12). In the second period (M13-M24), 200 posts were published via the project partners' owned channels, and in the third period (M25-M36), 149 posts were published via the project partners' owned channels. In total, project partners published 382 posts on their social media channels.

Across all project implementations, the consortium partners were active on various media channels, contributing both social media posts and press clippings. The most active partners in terms of posts and press clippings were CIT UPC, BIC and CCIPB, each reporting multiple posts and several press mentions. Other partners, including JSI, EITM, KIT, CUT and INNOGET, also contributed with varying levels of activity. Overall, the consortium's social media presence during the project implementation leaned towards LinkedIn, X (formerly Twitter), Facebook, and Instagram, reflecting the diverse channels used to reach the target audience.

Figure 17: Partners' activity on media in the M1-M36

1. INDUSAC on X

M1-M12

The project had an official X account. During the first year of the project implementation (M1–M12), 19 posts were published and 17 followers were gained.

M13-M24

The second project year showed a significant increase in activity and reach on the X platform.

The account published 140 posts, which resulted in 18,915 impressions and 256 likes. The number of followers increased fivefold from the first year, bringing the total to 94. This growth reflected a more active and targeted use of the platform, aligned with major project milestones, calls for participation, and promotion of co-creation activities (Figure 18).

Figure 18: X account in the M1-M12 and the M13-M24 period

M25-36

In the final year of the project, the INDUSAC account maintained a consistent publishing frequency, posting 90 times, reaching 34,686 impressions and generating 381 likes. The follower count grew steadily, reaching 100 followers by the end of the project. Content published during this period focused on project results, final events, video dissemination, and impact storytelling, further boosting visibility and engagement.

Figure 19: X account likes and impressions throughout all three periods

2. INDUSAC on LinkedIn

M13-M24

In August 2023, the INDUSAC consortium decided to set up an official project account on LinkedIn, following a suggestion from BIC. This decision was motivated by changes to the Twitter platform (renamed X), which led to a noticeable decline in user engagement and activity. In contrast, LinkedIn was deemed more appropriate for effectively reaching the project's target audience. The platform provides access to a diverse range of stakeholders, including companies, chambers of commerce, clusters, universities, individual students and researchers, and EU institutions.

Between M13 and M24, the INDUSAC consortium actively used LinkedIn to engage its target audiences. During this period, the LinkedIn account recorded 1,348 reactions, 28 comments, and 75 reposts. The account grew by 439 followers, all gained organically, without paid promotion. This growth and interaction reflect the platform's suitability for reaching companies, chambers of commerce, clusters, universities, students, researchers, and EU institutions.

M25-M36

In the final reporting period (M25–M36), the INDUSAC LinkedIn account continued to play a key role in reaching the project's diverse audience. Building on the foundation established in the previous period, LinkedIn proved to be an effective platform for engaging with companies, chambers of commerce, clusters, universities, students, researchers, and EU institutions.

Between M25–M36, the INDUSAC LinkedIn page achieved 26,343 impressions, 1,105 reactions, 25 comments, and 32 reposts.

This performance reflected sustained visibility and steady engagement throughout the final year of the project.

In terms of followers, the account grew by 158 organic followers, reaching a cumulative total of 597 by project end, all achieved organically without paid promotion.

The steady follower growth and continued audience interaction confirmed LinkedIn's suitability as a dissemination channel for INDUSAC. Regular updates, targeted posts, and promotion of project milestones and events helped maintain audience interest and reinforce the project's brand within the professional community.

Follower metrics

Figure 20: Followers metrics on LinkedIn in the M25-M36 period

3. INDUSAC on YouTube

M1-M12

In M6, the INDUSAC YouTube account was launched.

During the first year of the project, one video was published. The animation illustrates how the project enables quick, challenge-driven, and human-centred collaboration between industry and academia. It explains the process by which companies submit real-world challenges, form international teams of students and researchers, and deliver innovative solutions. The video highlights the benefits of the mechanism for all stakeholders and promotes the INDUSAC platform as a gateway to fostering European innovation.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=H1w7aadf84I>

M13-M24

During the period M13-M24, the recording from the Informative Virtual Event was added on 23 November 2023

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7gy_hs7WRdY&t

M25-M36

In the final reporting period (M25–M36), the INDUSAC YouTube account was updated with two new videos, bringing the total number of published videos to four:

- **"INDUSAC in a nutshell"** – a short animation about the concept of the project:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Z2f9nEWcWPg>
- **"INDUSAC for Students"** – a short promotional video targeting students and researchers, encouraging them to participate in the project's co-creation challenges:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2SCriGGPAgs>

Additionally, a final video from **EIT Manufacturing Day – Final Project Showcase** was prepared – a recap video summarising INDUSAC's presence and activities during the final event held in Vienna, including the last project workshop and stakeholder sessions:

<https://youtu.be/3DgkrD99kvc>

Throughout the project (M1–M36), the YouTube channel recorded: 326 total views, 12.3 hours of watch time, 18 subscribers gained, 469 impressions, 26.9% impression click-through rate, and an average view duration of 2:15 minutes.

These metrics, while modest, reflect consistent interest in INDUSAC's audio-visual content, particularly in support of online events and information sessions.

The platform proved valuable as a supplementary channel for engaging audiences who prefer video content, including students, researchers, and companies seeking an accessible way to understand the project's goals and achievements.

To maximise its potential, future similar projects could consider more frequent video updates, shorter highlight clips, and prominently embedding videos on the website and social media channels to drive more views and engagement.

Your channel has had 326 views so far

Figure 21: INDUSAC’s YouTube Channel views throughout the entire project

Figure 22: INDUSAC’s YouTube Channel statistics throughout the entire project

V. MEDIA (PRESS CLIPPINGS)

M1-M12

BIC, as the T4.1 leader, produced the first press release, which was distributed to consortium members (M6). The press release is also available as a PDF file on the INDUSAC website: <https://indusac.eu/media/> (Figure 23).

INDUSAC

The Quick Challenge-Driven, Human-Centred Co-Creation Mechanism for INDUstry-Academia Collaborations (INDUSAC) is a HORIZON EUROPE project.

The aim of the project is to develop and validate a state-of-the-art Industry-Academia Collaboration mechanism for quick, challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation.

The INDUSAC project designs a state-of-the-art mechanism for industry-academia collaboration that is based on human-centred design principles that enable quick project co-creation. At least 300 international co-creation projects are selected for implementation to ensure the validation of the mechanism. These micro-projects led by teams consisting of students, researchers, and company staff cover various activities to target numerous industrial sectors. They are expected to create a bridge between business and academia.

The INDUSAC project focuses on four areas:

- Circularity
- General Sustainability
- Digitalisation
- Industry 4.0

The INDUSAC project creates a dynamic community of industry-academia stakeholders, including at least 1000 companies, 3000 students, and 300 researchers by project end.

The project focuses on the mechanism's two main components:

- The INDUSAC platform is to build on pre-existing Industry-Academia Collaboration mechanisms to facilitate a user-friendly co-creation process. It provides the foundation for developing solutions that clearly process the needs and interests of companies, students, and researchers in the EU.
- The INDUSAC methodology aims to facilitate the creation of company, student, and researcher teams by matching industry needs with students' and researchers' interests and skills. The methodology is built on a baseline of pre-existing co-creation approaches and offers guidance packages, as well as processes and tools for its smooth functioning. It provides detailed user journey maps.

Open Calls

INDUSAC launches a continuous open call for universities. The aim is to engage with at least 15 organisations at the start of the open call and reach at least 30 by the end of it. The open call for universities and research centres will be open for 18 months, starting in September 2023. Once registered in the open call, the universities and research centres will promote participation in the competitions among their students, who will be able to express interest, join a team and submit their solutions to companies' challenges anytime during the open call. Each challenge will have a specific deadline during the open call, which will be announced two months in advance to allow a suitable reaction from the companies and students. INDUSAC will select 300 co-creation teams formed by at least three students from three different EU countries, who will receive the INDUSAC programme support grant.

The project started on 1st September 2022 and will run for three years.

Partnership

The project coordinator is Jozef Stefan Institute (Slovenia) and other partners are Bydgoszcz Industrial Cluster Teal Valley (Poland), Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Pápa-Bárapata (Hungary), Cyprus University of Technology (Cyprus), Bax & Company (Spain), UPC Technology Center (Spain), EIT Manufacturing East (Austria), Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (Germany), and Innoget (Spain).

WWW.INDUSAC.EU

Figure 23: INDUSAC press release

Press clippings per country

Figure 24: Press clippings per country in the M1-M12 period

Press clippings per geographical range

Figure 25: Press clippings per geographical range in the M1-M12 period

A total of 13 press clippings were reported, resulting in strong EU coverage in Poland and Hungary. What is more, 12 press clippings were published in the media at the EU level, and one press clipping at the global level (Figures 24 and 25).

M13-M24

In the second reporting period (M13-M24), two press releases were issued (Figure 26 and Figure 27):

- The first one, created by JSI, was an invitation to join the project. This content was shared with universities, companies, and cluster organisations, and later used for PPPs and KICs.
- The second press release, created by BIC, promoted the Open Call for students.

INDUSAC

Subject: Invitation for companies to be part of the INDUSAC project

Dear Sir or Madam,

On behalf of Białogórz Industrial Cluster Tool Valley and the INDUSAC project, we would like to invite your organisation to participate in an exciting new project aimed at strengthening the collaboration between industry and academia.

INDUSAC is a HORIZON EUROPE project that aims to develop and validate an Industry-Academia Collaboration mechanism. Within the project, we will facilitate a simple, user-friendly co-creation process that allows the development of solutions that address the needs and interests of companies in the EU, with special attention to widening and associated countries¹.

Companies are invited to register on the platform and prepare a non-confidential summary of a challenge they might be facing. The Challenge may be from nine general areas: (1) Customer needs (and product properties) of tomorrow, (2) Finding white spots in the product portfolio, (3) Marketing campaign of the future, (4) Feed the future platform - developing a digital platform based on a market analysis, (5) Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Persona), (6) Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Scenario), (7) Business plan - reduce your risk and optimise your planning, (8) Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain, and (9) Business model: Adding a service to my product - Building a PSS (product service system) (for details see the Appendix).

Selected international co-creation teams comprising 3-6 students and/or researchers will solve the companies' challenges within 4-6 weeks. The company does not have any financial obligations or commitments towards the co-creation team. INDUSAC has a budget of 900.000 EUR gross intended for student members of co-creation teams, where mini-grants of 3.000 EUR gross will be distributed among student members of each team.

By participating in the project company receives a solution to its challenge, gets an opportunity to meet young bright minds from across Europe to consider as future collaborators or employees, and increases its own visibility through international collaboration.

Timeline:

- **INDUSAC platform** for posting the company's challenges open in November 2023
- Motivation letters submitted by the co-creation teams in February 2024
- engagement from the company to guide the co-creation team foreseen for March & April 2024
- results from the co-creation team will be available in May 2024.

Two later cut-off dates for receiving new motivation letters will be available for new challenges. It is thus advisable that the challenges are relevant for a reasonable period of time.

We would be happy to provide you with more information about the project and its goals. If you are interested in learning more, please do not hesitate to contact us or visit the website www.indusac.eu.

Yours sincerely,

Partners of the INDUSAC consortium

WWW.INDUSAC.EU

¹ Widening and associated countries: Widening countries (Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Estonia, Greece, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Malta, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, <https://www.gov.uk/government/countries/associated-countries>) and Associated Countries (1. Albania, 2. Armenia, 3. Bosnia and Herzegovina, 4. Faroe Islands, 5. Georgia, 6. Jordan, 7. Israel, 8. Kosovo, 9. Moldova, 10. Montenegro, 11. North Macedonia, 12. Norway, 13. Serbia, 14. Tunisia, 15. Turkey, 16. Ukraine, 17. UK)

INDUSAC

Appendix: What kind of results can a company expect by posting a particular Challenge

Type of Challenge	Result to expect
Customer needs (and product properties) of tomorrow Development of future-robust product properties based on scenarios and trend analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scenario/trend analysis and references (e.g. World Economic Forum) • Catalogue of future robust product properties (e.g. Excel)
Finding white spots in the product portfolio Development of an action plan to improve and/or develop relevant clusters within the product portfolio's elements based on a strategic analysis of the product portfolio	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategic analysis of product portfolio (e.g. BCG-matrix) • Clustering of product portfolio (e.g. PowerPoint) • Action-plan /white spot analysis for relevant clusters
Marketing campaign of the future Design a marketing campaign based on a market analysis with a focus on customers and trend analysis.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Market analysis with a focus on customers • Trend analysis combining future customers and marketing trends • Design of a marketing campaign
Feed the future platform - developing a digital platform based on a market analysis Development of a digital platform prototype based on a market analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Market analysis to define the platform • Digital Platform prototype (click dummy) (based on existing product profiles)
Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Persona) Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple personas, and appropriate product properties	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Persona • Product Profile • Service/ Product idea
Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Scenario) Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple trends/scenarios, and appropriate future-robust product properties	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Persona • Product Profile • Service/ Product idea
Business plan - reduce your risk and optimise your planning The development of a business plan after a SWOT analysis and an estimation of profitability.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SWOT-Analysis • Business plan • Estimation of profitability
Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain Based on a specified customer need, new product ideas should be developed and shown in a virtual prototype.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of alternative product ideas • Utility analysis and evaluation of ideas • Virtual prototype
Business model: Adding a service to my product - Building a PSS The development of new business models for a given product.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Persona (user behaviour) • Business model • 3 alternatives and subsequent utility analysis

WWW.INDUSAC.EU

Figure 26: INDUSAC press release 1

INVITATION TO STUDENTS AND RESEARCHERS

We invite you to participate in the INDUSAC project -students can receive up to EUR 1000 gross/person!

FOR STUDENTS AND RESEARCHERS

Are you interested in participating in an international team of students and researchers?
 Would you like to connect with companies and students / researchers from all over Europe?
 Would you like to learn about working in a company?
 Do you like to solve challenges?

As part of the INDUSAC project, companies will prepare challenges for students/researchers from various fields. Students/researchers will be able to apply to solve these challenges in three- to six- member teams and solve the challenge within 2 months; students will receive a reward for solutions of up to EUR 1000 gross/person.

EXPRESS YOUR INTEREST AND APPLY

www.indusac.eu

Quick Challenge-Driven, Human-Centred Co-Creation Mechanism for Industry-Academia Collaborations

Figure 27: INDUSAC press release 2

A total of 13 press clippings were reported in M1-M12, whereas in the period M13-M24, partners reported 63 press clippings. That gives 76 press clippings in total from M1-M24, indicating strong EU coverage in Spain and Poland. What is more, 72 press clippings were published in the media at the EU level and four at the global level (Figures 28 and 29).

Figure 28: Press clippings per country in the M13-M24 period

Figure 29: Press clippings per geographical range in the M13-M24 period

M25-M36

In the final reporting period (M25–M36), communication and dissemination activities continued to receive significant media attention. During this period, the consortium partners reported a total of 109 additional press clippings across European and global media outlets. These clippings highlighted the project’s achievements, final outcomes, and its contribution to strengthening industry-academia collaboration.

The coverage during M25–M36 featured a strong presence in Spain, Poland, Hungary, and other countries, illustrating the broad geographical reach of the project’s dissemination of results in its final phase. Notable articles included insights into the project’s final event and its impact on students, researchers, and companies, with a particular emphasis on the final Manufacturing Day 2025 and the long-term benefits of the INDUSAC platform.

The press clippings in this period consisted of 108 clippings published at the EU or national level and one at the global level, maintaining a balanced outreach and visibility across regions.

1. Cumulative Summary of Press Clippings (M1–M36)

Across all three reporting periods (M1–M12, M13–M24, and M25–M36), the INDUSAC project garnered a total of **185 press clippings**:

- **M1–M12:** 13 press clippings
- **M13–M24:** 63 press clippings
- **M25–M36:** 109 press clippings

This demonstrated a consistent level of media interest and engagement, with the strongest coverage recorded in Spain, Poland, Cyprus, and Hungary.

Of the total 185 press clippings:

- **EU-level coverage:** 179 press clippings
- **Global-level coverage:** 6 press clippings

The media presence throughout the project reflected the consortium’s effective dissemination efforts, contributing to the project’s visibility and recognition as a model of innovative, human-centred co-creation in industry-academia collaboration.

VI. NEWSLETTER

M1-M12

During the first year of the project, one issue of the INDUSAC newsletter was created. The newsletter was sent out in April 2023 to inform about the project and its activities (Figure 30).

Figure 30: INDUSAC official newsletter

The newsletter has been published in an electronic format; Mailchimp was used to distribute it.

M13-24

Due to the low number of newsletter subscriptions on the website and, therefore, the limited final reach, the consortium decided during the Barcelona 2023 meeting to remove the newsletter from the project website and instead use the LinkedIn e-newsletter.

Four issues of the e-newsletter were published between M13 and M24, reaching almost 3,000 recipients (Figure 31).

Article totals ⓘ

2,840
Impressions

70
Engagements

NEWSLETTER

INDUSAC e-newsletter

Your industry compass! 📍 Stay on the pulse of R&D. Perfect for professionals, researchers & students. Subscribe now! 📧

By INDUSAC-HE
439 followers

Published monthly
221 subscribers

Figure 31: INDUSAC LinkedIn e-newsletter in detail

M25-36

In the final reporting period (M25–M36), the consortium maintained its dissemination strategy using the LinkedIn e-newsletter. During this period, the newsletter achieved 956 impressions, 23 engagements, and 245 article views.

These figures indicate sustained visibility and audience interest in the project updates during its concluding months. While lower than in the previous period (M13–M24), the newsletter continued to support the communication efforts by reinforcing INDUSAC’s message and promoting its final activities and results.

The consistent use of LinkedIn as the newsletter platform proved beneficial throughout the project, providing measurable outreach and engagement with the target audience.

1. Analysis of INDUSAC Newsletters (LinkedIn e-newsletters)

In response to the low uptake of the website-based newsletter in the first year, INDUSAC transitioned to a LinkedIn-based e-newsletter starting from M13, which continued through to the end of the project. Over the course of the project, seven issues of the newsletter were published on LinkedIn, each highlighting key updates, milestones, and opportunities for engagement.

Performance overview:

- Impressions per issue ranged from 45 to 463, with higher reach achieved in later editions as the subscriber base and awareness grew.
- Article views ranged from 20 (Issue 1) to 115 (Issue 6).
- Email open rates were generally healthy, averaging around 30–40%, peaking at 41% (Issue 2).
- Engagement rates were highest in the early issues, with Issue 1 reaching 37,8% engagement and Issue 2 at 28,6%, reflecting strong interest from the initial audience.
- Reactions and comments were modest across all issues, averaging ~10–20 reactions and very few reposts or comments.

Insights:

- The highest engagement rate and relative click-through rate occurred in the first two issues, likely due to novelty and early subscriber enthusiasm.
- Later issues maintained steady viewership, with slightly lower engagement rates (around 4–5%) but higher total impressions and email sends as the audience grew.
- The best-performing issue in absolute numbers was Issue 6, which achieved 115 article views, 167 email sends, and a 32% open rate.

Strengths:

- High open rates and consistent engagement despite no paid promotion.
- Steady growth of subscribers and impressions over time, showing that LinkedIn was a more effective channel than the previous Mailchimp newsletter.
- Topics resonated with the audience, sustaining interest over multiple editions.
- Areas for improvement (recommendations for future use):
 - Increase click-through rate beyond the consistent ~1–2% by incorporating more prominent calls to action and clear links to project outcomes or events.
 - Encourage more interaction (comments, shares) by asking questions or including polls in posts accompanying the newsletters.
 - Use more varied formats (e.g., video snippets, infographics) embedded in newsletter articles to enhance visual appeal.

2. Conclusion

The shift to LinkedIn newsletters proved successful, achieving greater visibility and audience engagement compared to the initial website-based approach. With 276 subscribers by the end of the project and steadily growing metrics, the LinkedIn e-newsletter effectively supported INDUSAC's communication objectives, reaching and maintaining a relevant professional audience throughout.

VII. EVENTS

M1-M12

From September 2022 until August 2023, the INDUSAC consortium organised two official events to present INDUSAC's opportunities to students (Table 1).

Name of event	Date	Physical/Online
Manufacturing Day 2023	2023/06/01	Physical
Cyprus Talks Green	2023/06/29	Physical

Table 1: Official INDUSAC events M1-M12

Figure 32: Manufacturing Day 2023

As for partners' activity, in M1-M12, the INDUSAC consortium attended three events: one national and two international. During their participation in the events, the consortium members presented opportunities from the INDUSAC project to students and researchers.

Figure 33: Presentation of INDUSAC at the BioFair 2023 in Ljubljana, Slovenia, where attendees were informed about the upcoming INDUSAC Call for Students and Researchers

M13-M24

As for partners' activity, in M13-M24, the INDUSAC consortium attended 25 events, mostly international. During their participation in the events, the consortium members presented opportunities from the INDUSAC project to students and researchers.

Figure 34: The Cutting Edge 2023 event in Ljubljana, Slovenia where INDUSAC opportunities were presented to students via leaflets.

Figure 35: INNOFORM, Bydgoszcz, Poland

M25-M36

In the final reporting period (M25–M36), the consortium continued its strong presence at international, national, and regional events, showcasing INDUSAC's results and promoting its outcomes to diverse audiences.

Between July 2024 and July 2025, the consortium partners participated in 29 events, including several high-profile international conferences such as the European Manufacturing Conference 2024 in Brussels, the Big Science Business Forum 2024 in

Trieste, and the 27th International Conference on Engineering and Product Design Education in Malta.

These events provided excellent opportunities to disseminate the project's final achievements and engage stakeholders from industry, academia, and policy. The final Manufacturing Day in Vienna in May 2025 was a notable highlight, marking the official wrap-up of the project with significant visibility.

Figure 36: BIC Team during AI Conference in 2024, Warsaw, Poland

Figure 37: INDUSAC Final Event during EIT Manufacturing Day 2025, Vienna, Austria

1. Cumulative summary of events M1-M36

Over the course of the entire INDUSAC project (M1–M36), the consortium maintained an active and visible presence by organising and participating in 57 events at national, regional, European, and global levels. The first reporting period (M1–M12) laid the foundation with three initial events, which helped introduce the project's vision to key stakeholders. In the second reporting period (M13–M24), this momentum grew substantially, with 25 events showcasing project activities, promoting calls for participation, and engaging diverse audiences. In the final reporting period (M25–M36), the consortium

continued its outreach with another 29 events, strategically focusing on disseminating results, sharing impact stories, and strengthening the project's legacy.

These events encompassed a wide variety of formats, including high-level conferences, trade fairs, exhibitions, hackathons, career fairs, and networking sessions. Through these engagements, the consortium highlighted the project's achievements, promoted the innovative co-creation mechanism, and created opportunities for dialogue among students, researchers, industry professionals, and policy makers.

Altogether, the INDUSAC consortium's sustained presence at events throughout the project enabled it to reach an estimated audience of over 263,000 individuals, demonstrating both the wide geographical reach and the strong interest in the project's approach to fostering industry-academia collaboration. By maintaining consistent participation at prominent international and regional events, the project not only amplified its visibility and credibility but also reinforced its role as a pioneering initiative in human-centred, challenge-driven co-creation between academia and industry.

The list of events attended in M1–M36 is presented in Table 2.

Partner	Start date	End date	Name of the event	City	Country	Geographic range
BIC	2022-11-08	2022-11-08	BIC Forum Przedsiębiorczości Akademickiej	Toruń	Poland	Regional
INNOGET	2023-01-18	2023-01-19	Advancing Economic Paradiplomacy - Unveiling Opportunities and Best Practices	Bonn	Germany	International
CCIPB	2023-05-17	2023-05-17	Ipar napjai (Days of Industry)	Budapest	Hungary	International
JSI	2023-05-17	2023-05-18	BioFair 2023	Ljubljana	Slovenia	National
EITM	2023-06-01	2023-06-01	Manufacturing Day	Vienna	Austria	International
CUT	2023-06-29	2023-06-29	Cyprus Talks Green	Nicosia	Cyprus	National
JSI	2023-07-05	2023-07-05	V. Konferenca slovenskih mladih raziskovalcev in študentov iz sveta in Slovenije (V. Conference of Slovenian Young Researchers and Students from Slovenia and Abroad)	Ljubljana	Slovenia	International

Partner	Start date	End date	Name of the event	City	Country	Geographic range
JSI	2023-09-21	2023-09-21	Cutting Edge 2023	Ljubljana	Slovenia	International
JSI	2023-09-29	2023-09-29	European Researchers' Night	Ljubljana	Slovenia	International
JSI	2023-10-11	2023-10-13	16th International Technology Transfer Conference	Ljubljana	Slovenia	International
KIT	2023-10-29	2023-11-02	IMECE 23	New Orleans	United States	International
BAX	2023-11-08	2023-11-09	Smart Cities World Expo Congress	Barcelona	Spain	International
CIT	2023-11-08	2023-11-09	Smart Cities World Expo Congress 2023	Barcelona	Spain	International
BAX	2023-11-10	2023-11-10	EIT Innoenergy Hackathon	Barcelona	Spain	International
JSI	2023-11-28	2023-11-28	Young Hopes 2023, entrepreneurial training for young researchers	Ljubljana	Slovenia	National
INNOGET	2023-12-04	2023-12-04	Cei Bcn - India & Barcelona Collaboration Opportunities Debate	Barcelona	Spain	International
CIT	2024-02-26	2024-02-29	MWC Barcelona 2024	Barcelona	Spain	International
BAX	2024-03-04	2024-03-06	JEC World	Paris	France	International
BIC	2024-03-12	2024-04-12	Conference "Forma wtryskowa i jej otoczenie"	Bydgoszcz	Poland	Regional
CIT	2024-03-20	2024-03-22	ForoTransfiere 2024	Malaga	Spain	International
INNOGET	2024-03-20	2024-03-20	FORO TRANSIFIERE	Malaga	Spain	International
BIC	2024-03-21	2024-03-21	Career Fair – YOUR FUTURE 2024	Bydgoszcz	Poland	Regional
JSI	2024-03-23	2024-03-23	Open Days at the Jožef Stefan Institute	Ljubljana	Slovenia	International
INNOGET	2024-03-26	2024-03-29	Tektite 2024:Digital Economy	Seoul	South Korea	International
BAX	2024-04-15	2024-04-18	TRA 2024	Dublin	Ireland	International

Partner	Start date	End date	Name of the event	City	Country	Geographic range
BIC	2024-04-16	2024-04-16	INNOFORM trade fair	Bydgoszcz	Poland	International
CCIPB	2024-04-18	2024-04-19	PollackExpo	Pécs	Hungary	International
CCIPB	2024-05-09	2024-05-10	Ipar napjai (Days of Industry)	Budapest	Hungary	International
JSI	2024-05-09	2024-05-09	Job opportunities fair 2024 (Sejem zaposlitvenih priložnosti)	Ljubljana	Slovenia	National
CIT	2024-05-13	2024-05-15	IOT Solutions World Congress 2025	Barcelona	Spain	International
JSI	2024-05-14	2024-05-15	BioFair 2024	Ljubljana	Slovenia	National
KIT	2024-05-20	2024-05-23	DESIGN 24	Dubrovnik	Croatia	International
CIT	2024-05-21	2024-05-23	IOT Solutions World Congress 2024	Barcelona	Spain	International
INNOGET	2024-05-22	2024-05-24	latitude59	Tallin	Estonia	International
EITM	2024-06-06	2024-06-06	Manufacturing Day	Vienna	Austria	International
INNOGET	2024-06-17	2024-06-19	Tech Connect	Washington	USA	International
INNOGET	2024-06-26	2024-06-26	Open Innovation Forum	Cambridge	UK	International
BIC	2024-09-01	2024-09-01	Business breakfast for BIC members	Bydgoszcz	Poland	Regional
EITM	2024-09-24	2024-09-25	European Manufacturing Conference 2024	Brussels	Belgium	International
JSI	2024-10-01	2024-10-04	Big Science Business Forum 2024	Trieste	Italy	International
CCIPB	2024-10-08	2024-10-20	Design Pécs program series and exhibition	Pécs	Hungary	National
JSI	2024-10-09	2024-10-09	17th International Technology Transfer Conference	Ljubljana	Slovenia	International
JSI	2024-10-22	2024-10-22	BEST Dnevi znanosti 2024	Ljubljana	Slovenia	National
BIC	2024-10-25	2024-10-25	Conference "AI - Nowa Era Innowacji"	Warszawa	Poland	National
CIT	2024-11-05	2024-11-07	Smart Cities World Expo Congress 2024	Barcelona	Spain	International

Partner	Start date	End date	Name of the event	City	Country	Geographic range
CCIPB	2024-11-07	2024-11-07	Hovatovább' career guidance exhibiton and fair	Pécs	Hungary	Regional
JSI	2024-11-21	2024-11-21	Alumni JUMP	Ljubljana	Slovenia	National
CCIPB	2024-11-29	2024-11-29	Okos megoldások' conference	Pécs	Hungary	Regional
CIT	2025-02-24	2025-03-26	ForoTransfiere 2025	Malaga	Spain	International
CIT	2025-03-03	2025-03-06	MWC Barcelona 2025	Barcelona	Spain	International
BIC	2025-03-27	2025-03-27	Career Fair – YOUR FUTURE 2025	Bydgoszcz	Poland	Regional
BIC	2025-04-03	2025-06-03	INNOFORM trade fair	Bydgoszcz	Poland	International
EITM	2025-04-08	2025-04-10	InnoHive 2025	Brussels	Belgium	International
EITM	2025-05-09	2025-09-05	Manufacturing Day	Vienna	Austria	International
CCIPB	2025-05-12	2025-05-16	Ipar napjai (Days of Industry)	Budapest	Hungary	International
KIT	2025-10-10	2025-12-10	27th International Conference on Engineering and Product Design Education	Valetta	Malta	International
CIT	2025-11-04	2025-11-06	Smart Cities World Expo Congress 2025	Barcelona	Spain	International

Table 2: The list of events attended in M1–M36

VIII. SUMMARY

The communication and dissemination actions carried out by the consortium from M1 to M36 are summarised in Table 3.

Activity related	Indicator	Performance	Status M1-M12	Status M13-M24	Status M25-M36	In total
Communication, dissemination	Project visual identity (PVI)	PVI manual to be distributed among partners before M3	DONE	DONE	DONE	DONE
	Website	> 4,000 visits throughout the project	112	17,777 DONE	19,654	37,543
		> 15,000 pages viewed	243	29,971 DONE	31,827	62,041
		> 2,000 users	47	9,732 DONE	12,023	21,802
	Social Media	>100 X (f. Twitter) followers	17	77	6	100 DONE
		LinkedIn followers	-	439	158	597
		>20 social media posts on the partner's account	33 DONE	200	149	382
	Media Relations	> 4 press releases (media)	1	2	1	4 DONE
		> 20 articles published in European outlets	13	34 DONE	18	65
	Audio-visual materials	Flyer and rollup designed in M3 and updated in M32	DONE – M3	DONE	DONE – M32	DONE
		General presentation of the project (M6) and updated in M32; Poster layout designed in M6 and updated to M32	DONE – M6	DONE	DONE – M32	DONE
	Audio-visual materials	YouTube channel	DONE	DONE	DONE	DONE

Table 3: INDUSAC Key Performance Indicators

During the project's implementation, the INDUSAC consortium closely monitored the effectiveness of its dissemination and communication activities. The process began with detailed guidance on communication strategies and the utilisation of marketing materials after the kick-off meeting in September 2022. The consortium actively disseminated

information during project launch, event promotion, and regional outreach, and this dissemination was closely monitored.

BIC facilitated the monitoring process through the "Partners' actions reporting dashboard", which provided an overview of consortium dissemination activities. The dashboard tracked various dissemination channels, including press clippings, social media, newsletters, events, and scientific publications. Regular dashboard updates enabled close monitoring of dissemination efforts and timely adjustments to communication strategies.

The INDUSAC website emerged as a crucial tool for disseminating project-related information. Analysis of visitor profiles revealed significant engagement, with English as the primary language of access. Visitors from diverse geographic regions accessed the website, indicating its global reach and relevance.

Social media dissemination activities, primarily through X and LinkedIn, yielded positive results, with a notable increase in followers and engagement over time. Press clippings and media coverage further amplified project visibility, particularly within the EU.

The launch of the INDUSAC YouTube channel and the distribution of newsletters broadened outreach and engagement. Additionally, participation in events, organised by the consortium, individual partners or third parties, and attended by partners, facilitated direct interaction with stakeholders and promoted project opportunities.

In conclusion, the monitoring process demonstrated the evolving impact of dissemination and communication efforts throughout the project duration. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) continued to rise as dissemination activities persisted. Regular reporting and updates ensured ongoing evaluation and refinement of communication strategies to maximise project impact.

IX. RECOMMENDATIONS

As part of WP4's efforts to collectively increase the project's reach to its target audiences, WP4 developed and shared the following strategy with all partners to implement where appropriate. This strategy remains relevant beyond the project's lifetime as a guide for sustaining and scaling the impact of INDUSAC's achievements:

1. Utilise Industry-Specific Platforms

- **Professional Networks:** Continue leveraging platforms like LinkedIn for professionals and ResearchGate for researchers to share challenges and solutions.
- **Community Platforms:** Explore emerging platforms, such as Bluesky and Mastodon, which some audiences are migrating to.

2. Content Marketing

- **Case Studies and White Papers:** Publish detailed case studies and white papers that outline successful challenges and solutions.
- **Impact Stories:** Share personal success stories from participating students, researchers, and companies to inspire others.
- **Industry Blogs and Magazines:** Continue contributing articles to respected industry blogs, magazines, and newsletters to reach a broader audience.

3. Webinars and Online Workshops

- **Live Sessions:** Host webinars and online workshops with industry experts to discuss the challenges and potential solutions.
- **Interactive Q&A:** Include interactive Q&A sessions to engage participants directly.
- **On-Demand Content:** Offer recordings of sessions for on-demand viewing, catering to broader time zones and availability.

4. Social Media Campaigns

- **Targeted Campaigns:** Use LinkedIn and emerging channels for targeted campaigns focusing on industry professionals.
- **Regular Updates:** Maintain an active presence with regular updates about challenges, deadlines, and success stories.
- **Visual Content:** Incorporate more video and infographic formats to increase engagement.
- **Student Outreach:** Promote specific challenges aimed at attracting students to apply.

5. Email Marketing

- **Personalised Content:** Send personalised emails with content relevant to each segment, including invitations to participate in challenges, updates, and resources.
- **Segmentation:** Use audience segmentation to tailor content more precisely to stakeholders' profiles and needs.

6. Collaborations and Partnerships

- **Industry Associations:** Strengthen ties with industry associations and professional bodies to promote challenges through their channels.
- **Academic Institutions:** Continue to collaborate with universities and research institutions to reach researchers and innovators.
- **Cross-Project Synergies:** Explore synergies with other EU-funded projects addressing similar objectives.

7. Conferences and Trade Shows

- **Booths and Presentations:** Participate in industry conferences and trade shows with booths and presentations showcasing results.
- **Networking Events:** Host or sponsor networking events at these conferences to engage directly with potential participants.
- **Final Results Roadshow:** Consider presenting final results as a roadshow or at key industry events beyond the project's end.

8. Monitoring and Adaptation

- **Impact Measurement:** Implement simple tracking (e.g., UTM links, feedback surveys) to monitor the effectiveness of dissemination activities.
- **Continuous Improvement:** Regularly review and refine outreach strategies based on audience feedback and analytics.

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